

The Special Relativistic $\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ Factor and the Notion of Length in (0,ct) Part III

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In Parts I and II, we tried to speculate why time in a rest frame (particle with rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t) should exist. In particular, it might seem a little arbitrary to assign a time t even if there is a clock on the wall, but nothing is happening to the particle. As a result, we tried to map the state $(x=0, t)$ to the state $(x=L, t=0)$, where $L=vt$. Here $-v$ could be the velocity of a moving frame (constant velocity). In a previous note (1), we also tried to suggest that $(x=0, t)$ means that one continuously measures the $x=0$ position and this set of measurements constitutes points in time, i.e. defines time.

In this note, we consider how time may be thought of as length in two ways. First, we consider that $(x=0, t=0)$ and $(x=0, t)$, when seen in the moving frame, are $(x'=0, t'=0)$, $(x'=gvt, t'=gt)$ where $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. In other words, the presence of a time in the rest frame for $x=0$, means that in the moving frame there must still be time and this implies that the particle has moved $v(t'-0)$. In other words, a time in the rest frame implies a length in the moving frame. A second approach is to consider the idea of (1) that time means numerous position measurements. If one takes a measurement every dt using light (on a classical mass), then the light may travel $dx = c dt$ for each measurement and the measurements t map to a length ct .

Finally, we consider the mass at $(x=0, t=0)$ in the rest frame and send a photon in the y direction at $t=0$. At time t , it will have reached a certain height. This height should have nothing to do with what is seen in a moving frame and so one is able to create an invariant for each frame and derive the factor $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ such that $t'=gt$. This holds because c , the speed of light in a vacuum, is the same in the rest and moving frames.

Massive Particle at Rest

A classical particle at rest at $x=0, t$ may have a time assigned due to a clock in the room, but one might try to argue that there is no sense of time if there are no interactions. We thus try to consider how to interpret this t .

As a first step, one may consider $(x=0, t=0)$ and $(x=0, t)$ and perform a Lorentz transformation on each. In a moving frame with constant $-v$, a particle must be seen to be moving with speed v . Furthermore, if the particle was at $(0,0)$, it Lorentz transforms to $(0,0)$. $(x=0, t)$, however, implies a length in the moving frame. In particular:

$$(x=0, t) \rightarrow (gvt, gt) \text{ where } g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc} \text{ ((1))}$$

Thus, even though nothing happens to the particle in the rest frame from $(x=0, t=0)$ and $(x=0, t)$, it is possible that something happened. In other words, speed is frame relative and “nothing happens” only in the $v=0$ frame. In every other frame, the particle moves with v (modified time) and so there must be some length.

A second way to consider the situation is to argue that $(x=0, t=0)$ and $(x=0, t)$ differ in that numerous measurements (bounding light of the massive particle) have occurred between $t=0$

and t . In other words, t is a measure of the possible measurements which may have occurred. If these measurements are done every dt using light, then:

T is equivalent to a length of: $(t/dt) c dt = ct$ ((2))

In other words, ct is a length.

Deriving the factor $g(v)=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$

We consider a third manner of defining a length related to t in $(x=0, t)$. At $(x=0, t=0)$, one releases a photon vertically (along the y axis). This photon travels a distance ct in the time t . In the moving frame, one would see a particle moving with speed v and so the photon would move for $ct' = vgt$ at an angle such that its x projection travels vt' . Here $g(v)$ is assumed to be unknown. This means that along the vertical, the distance traveled is $\sqrt{cc-vv} t'$. If the y distances should be the same in the rest and moving frame, then:

$Ct = \sqrt{cc-vv} g t$ or $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ ((3))

Thus, there is a modification factor for time in the moving frame when one applies a Lorentz transformation to $(x=0, ct)$.

In this example, we see that the notion of time is linked to length via a second object, the moving photon, which does not interact with the particle. In other words, one may have an object at rest and argue that time is superfluous because no interactions occur involving the particle. There may, however, be other particles which are interacting in the interval $t=0$ to t and these interactions define time for these particles. The point is that if one of these particles were to react with the particle at rest, one would need to carry over the t of this non-rest particle to identify the time at which this interaction occurs. This suggests that there is time even if a particle is at rest and not interacting. Time does not necessarily have to describe a set of events for a given particle at rest (seemingly doing nothing), it could describe events for other particles which may interact with the rest particle at t .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider whether assigning a t to a particle at rest, i.e. $(x=0, t)$ is superfluous. This, however, does not seem to be the case for two reasons. If viewed from a moving frame, t suggests that the particle has moved a distance of $v^* t$ (modified time). In other words $(x=0, t=0)$ and $(x=0, t)$ are not the same when viewed from a moving frame. Secondly, one may argue, as in (1), that t is really a measure of possible $x=0$ position measurements made by bouncing light from the object. These represent a distance of ct as argued above.

Finally, we consider releasing a photon in the y direction. By the time t , it has traveled ct . In the moving frame, $t=0, t$ is represented by $t'=0, t'=g(v)t$. In such a case, one has a right angle triangle with ct' on the hypotenuse, $v t'$ along the x' -axis and $\sqrt{cc-vv} t'$ along the y' axis. Equating distance along the y axis and y' axis yields $g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Spacetime with Time Defined Through an Interaction Measuring Space? (preprint, zenodo, 2024)